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Optimization of a Deep Neural Network on Intel OpenVino for a Pedestrian Detection Algorithm

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Abstract

In order to control an automatic traffic light system so that it switches when a pedestrian arrives, a system is needed that recognizes people in images. Nowadays, this is done with computer vision models based on neural networks. These technologies achieve excellent results but require a considerable amount of computing power. The computational capacity of a device affects the result of a model and should be taken into consideration. For situations where computational power reaches its limits, models such as Tensorflow's SSD Mobilenet-v2 can be used. In addition, several optimization methods and techniques can be applied to further increase the performance of a model. This can be especially important in traffic situations due to the potential hazards involved. Therefore, this thesis investigates different types and methods of optimizations that can be performed on an SSD Mobilenet-v2 in the context of a pedestrian-detecting traffic light. The network was run on an Intel NUC computer, which offers a CPU, GPU and VPU. Among other things, the Intel OpenVino framework was used to perform specific optimizations. It is shown in this work that one can achieve a significant increase in precision and keep an execution time well below 100ms. The appropriate choice of dataset and subsets represent a large leap in accuracy. By diversifying the data, 20-25% better results were obtained. Furthermore, different combinations of image augmentation methods were tested. These affected the colouring of the images and resulted in a 1% improvement in precision. In addition, adjusting the learning rate resulted in a potential increase of 1-2%. However, an accuracy loss of 4-14% of the Open Vino model conversion was observed for the SSD Mobilenet-v2. In addition, the inference times depend on the executing device and the resolution of the images. Overall, the GPU and a resolution of 640×480 px proved to be the best choice. With a 16-bit quantized network at the before-mentioned image quality, no noticeable loss of accuracy was observed with an execution time of 16ms. Overall, these results show that a significant performance increase can be expected with appropriate optimizations. OpenVino proved to be an advantage due to a strong decrease in execution times, but care must be taken when converting different models.

Kurzfassung

Um ein automatisches Ampelsystem so anzusteuern, dass es bei einem ankommenden Passanten umschaltet, braucht man ein System das Menschen auf Bildern erkennt. Dies wird heutzutage mit Computer Vision Modellen gemacht, die auf neuronalen Netzen beruhen. Diese Technologien erzielen sehr gute Ergebnisse sind aber mit einem beträchtlichen Rechenaufwand verbunden. Die Rechenkapazität eines Gerätes beeinflusst das Ergebnis eines Modells und ist in Betracht zu ziehen. Für Situationen, in denen die Rechenleistung schnell an ihre Grenzen stößt, können Modelle wie das SSD Mobilenet-v2 von Tensorflow verwendet werden. Zusätzlich können eine Reihe von Optimierungsmethoden und Verfahren eingesetzt werden, um die Leistung eines Modells noch weiter zu steigern. Dies kann vor allem in Verkehrssituationen aufgrund der potenziellen Gefahren von Bedeutung sein. Deswegen untersucht die vorliegende Arbeit verschiedene Arten und Ausführungen von Optimierungen, die an einem SSD Mobilenet-v2 im Kontext einer Personenerkennenden Ampel vorgenommen werden können. Das Netz sollte dabei auf einem Intel-NUC Computer laufen, der einen CPU, GPU und VPU aufweist. Dabei wurde unter anderem vom Intel OpenVino Framework Gebrauch gemacht, um gewisse Optimierungen vorzunehmen. Es wird in dieser Arbeit gezeigt, dass man einen deutliche Präzisionssteigerung erzielen und eine Ausführungszeit auf weit unter 100ms halten kann. Die geeignete Wahl des Datensets und der Subsets repräsentiert einen großen Sprung in Genauigkeit. Durch Diversifizierung der Daten wurden 20-25% bessere Ergebnisse erzielt. Des Weiteren wurden verschiedene Kombinationen von Image Augmentationsmethoden getestet, welche die Färbung der Bilder verändert. Dies resultierte in einer Verbesserung der Präzision von 1%. Zudem ergab die Anpassung der Learning Rate hingegen eine potenzielle Erhöhung von 1-2%. Allerdings wurde ein Genauigkeitsverlust von 4-14% der Open Vino Modell Konvertierung für das SSD Mobilenet-v2 festgestellt. Darüber hinaus hängen die Inferenzzeiten von dem ausführenden Gerät und der Auflösung der Bilder ab. Insgesamt erwies sich der GPU und eine Auflösung von 640×480 px als beste Wahl. Mit einem 16-bit quantisiertem Netzwerk bei genannter Bildqualität wurde kein merkbarer Genauigkeitsverlust festgestellt und eine Geschwindigkeit von 16ms gemessen. Insgesamt zeigen diese Resultate, dass man durch entsprechende Optimierungen einen deutlichen Leistungsanstieg erwarten kann. OpenVino erwies sich als ein Vorteil durch eine starke Abnahme der Ausführungszeiten jedoch gilt Vorsicht zu walten bei der Konvertierung von verschiedenen Modellen.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, humans found themselves surrounded by artificial intelligence. From the food we eat [Tal+20] to the media we consume, machine learning spread its way into many aspects of our day-to-day lives. This technological advancement is driven by a thirst for automation, productivity and our society's welfare. An example of automation would be the autonomous switching of traffic lights based on the current traffic situation. To achieve this, one would need a system that efficiently recognizes related objects and predicts their intentions to adopt the traffic light accordingly. As a result, this thesis aims to investigate solutions to detect pedestrians in traffic as precisely as possible while optimizing these approaches for them to operate in an environment with limited resources.

1.1 Motivation

This thesis is part of a project intending to design a system that predicts pedestrian intentions to switch the traffic lights for a pedestrian crossing [Ert+18]. However, to recognize a pedestrian's intent, one must first identify a person, which is the focus of this thesis. The detection is achieved by mounting a camera at a pedestrian crossing. The device should be attached at an elevated viewpoint with an Intel-NUC computer that takes care of the needed computations.

This problem is by no means new and has also already been researched at [Ert+18] and [Ert+17]. However, the detection algorithm was a custom-built SSD model with an AlexNet as the backbone network. Although the detection worked well, there was still room for improvement in precision and time. Therefore, the paper suggests using a Mobilenet detector, and this thesis aims to investigate ways to optimize the performance of an SSD Mobilenet-v2 architecture for this use case.

1.2 Problem

The goal is to examine optimization methods that can be leveraged before, during and after training of an SSD Mobilenet-v2 while specific requirements of speed and accuracy have to be met. The research question is, therefore: **How can an SSD Mobilenet-v2 be optimized for a pedestrian detection problem on an Intel-NUC computer?**

1.3 Task

The following functional requirements have been defined:

- Time: The mean latency shall be less than 100 ms.
- Precision: The mean Average Precision (mAP) at 0.5 IoU shall be used as a metric. The target is to have a maximum of 2% precision loss compared to our best-performing network.

Furthermore, a pre-trained SSD Mobilenet-v2 will serve as a base model, along with the Tensorflow 2 Object Detection API framework as a training framework. Then most measurements will take place on an Intel-NUC computer with a GPU and CPU. Moreover, the performance of an Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 plugged into the NUC via USB will also be tested. Finally, the computer will run with Intel's OpenVINO toolkit, which will serve as the inference framework.

1.4 Methodology

An experimental approach will be followed where a set of separate experiments have been defined. These investigate certain aspects of neural network optimization to study their effect on the performance metrics. Therefore, the following tasks will have to be completed to conduct these experiments:

- Prepare dataset: Three different datasets have been chosen. These need to be processed and harmonized.
- Prepare hardware: A training and measurement environment needs to be set up for the experiments while trying to automate as much as possible of the processes.
- Train network variations: Networks will be trained with different sets of hyperparameters and optimization methods that all use the base model as a starting point.
- Measure performance: This is where the actual measurements of the two target metrics will take place.
- Analyze results: The different versions of the SSD Mobilenet-v2 will be compared.

After completing these steps, the best combination of optimization methods should become apparent.

Chapter 2

State of the art

This chapter will focus on explaining the technologies utilized during this thesis. First, the architecture and use of an SSD Mobilenet-v2 will be explored, and then the attention will be turned to Tensorflow's Object Detection API. Afterwards, Intel's OpenVINO Toolkit and the dataset used for this thesis will be investigated. The goal here is to give an overview of these technologies. This should show the reader why these have been chosen for this thesis.

2.1 SSD Mobilenet-v2

The Computer Vision field has advanced thanks to the development and use of convolutional neural networks. These powerful constructs are widely used for Object Detection, Object Classification, and Object Recognition purposes [Chi+20, p.1]. Unfortunately, this often comes with a severe load of computing power, and there are many cases like the one from this thesis where performance is limited. This raises the need for more efficient networks tailored to these applications. For this thesis, an SSD Mobilenet-v2 has been chosen. This model is part of Tensorflow's Object Detection API and is often used for embedded applications because of its efficiency [Chi+20, p.1].

The SSD Mobilenet-v2 is a single-stage detection model that takes image pixels as input and outputs bounding box coordinates and class probabilities for all image detections. However, what makes this model more efficient than regular convolutional neural networks? Two network architectures are being combined and give SSD Mobilenet-v2 its characteristics:

- Mobilenets
- Single-shot detection

These architectures arose from the need for a less computational intensive object detection system. At the time, state-of-the-art detectors performed poorly in real-time applications. For instance, the faster R-CNN could only work at seven frames per second, even though it was the most advanced network. This framerate made it and other networks unusable for embedded systems [Liu+16].

2.1.1 Mobilenets

Mobilenet-v1

A neural network can and is usually composed of different layers. Specifically, convolutional neural networks are neural networks that contain convolutional layers [KSH17, p.1]. These are based on convolution operations that filter features out of the image and output them as a feature map. However, Mobilenet-v1 makes use of depthwise separable convolutions. These have been introduced in this paper [How+17, p.2]. It presents a mathematical proof of how they reduce the computational cost that will be investigated now.

Assuming a convolutional layer takes as input feature map \mathbf{F} of size $D_F \times D_F \times N$ and computes an output feature map of size \mathbf{G} of $D_F \times D_F \times M$. M represents the number of input channels, N is the number of output channels, and D_F is the spatial width and height of a square input feature map. Let us further suppose our convolutional layer is parametrized by the convolutional kernel \mathbf{K} of size $D_K \times D_K \times M \times N$. D_K is the square spatial dimension of the kernel. The following equation then links the output, input and kernel:

$$\mathbf{G}_{k,l,n} = \sum_{i,j,m} \mathbf{K}_{i,j,m,n} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{k+i-1,l+j-1,m} \quad (2.1)$$

from which the computational cost of convolutions can be derived:

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (2.2)$$

However, Mobilenet-v1's architecture is based on depthwise separable convolutions. These differ from their regular counterparts by a simple principle: Splitting the filtering and combining of features into two separate processes. This is achieved by dividing a standard convolutional layer into a depthwise convolutional layer and a pointwise convolutional layer. The depthwise convolution first applies a single filter for each input channel. This can be calculated with:

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{k,l,n} = \sum_{i,j,m} \hat{\mathbf{K}}_{i,j,m,n} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{k+i-1,l+j-1,m} \quad (2.3)$$

Where $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ is the depthwise convolutional kernel of size $D_K \times D_K \times M$ and $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ is the filtered output feature map. Afterwards, the pointwise convolution still needs to be applied. The latter consists of creating a linear combination of the depthwise output. All in all, this results in a total computational cost of:

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot D_F \cdot D_F + M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (2.4)$$

Which is the sum of the computational cost of the depthwise convolution (first summand) and the pointwise convolution (second summand). Let us now compare the results of 2.2 and 2.4:

$$\frac{D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot D_F \cdot D_F + M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F}{D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F} = \frac{1}{N} + \frac{1}{D_K^2} \quad (2.5)$$

As can be seen from equation 2.5, depthwise separable convolutions reduce computation by a factor of $\frac{1}{N} + \frac{1}{D_k^2}$. One more thing to note is that both depthwise and pointwise layers are followed by batch normalization and ReLU non-linearity layers. [How+17, p.2-3]

Mobilenet-v2

Mobilenet-v2 builds on using depthwise separable convolutions from Mobilenet-v1 by improving its structure further. First, the updated network introduces bottleneck layers alongside the depthwise separable convolutions. These are 1x1 convolutions that have fewer output channels than input channels. The bottleneck layers are used to reduce the network's number and dimensionality of feature maps. This decrease is often wanted since the number and dimensionality increase the deeper one goes into the network. Consequently, the calculations of the following convolutions become more complex. In Mobilenet-v2, bottleneck layers are placed before and after a depthwise separable convolution. Furthermore, these layers are linear because experimental evidence proposed that using non-linear bottlenecks destroys too much information and thus decreases performance. [San+18, p.4511-4512]

Another improved aspect is using residual connections between different layers [San+18, p.4512]. These connections attach the output of a previous convolutional layer with the input of a later convolutional layer. The regular input of the later convolutional layer is then combined with the prior by using a sum. This allows information to pass through parts of the network. Layers from the start of a residual connection to the end of a residual connection are called a residual block [He+16]. As a result, there are multiple ways of laying out these residual blocks in a network. This organization depends on which layers are chosen as a start- or endpoint. When residual connections were first introduced, the blocks were laid out like in figure 2.1a. As can be seen, the start and endpoint are layers with a higher number of channels. In Mobilenet-v2, the connections are made between the bottleneck layers like in figure 2.1b. This is called an inverted residual block and is more memory efficient than its regular counterparts. [San+18, p.4512-4513]

Figure 2.1: Comparison of original residual block and inverted residual block. The thickness of a block indicates the relative number of channels. Layers coloured in grey are linear.

2.1.2 Single-shot detection

Figure 2.2: 3 Stages of an SSD network. Note that the intermediate output between the stages has been marked red for clarification purposes.

The second network architecture utilized by SSD Mobilenet-v2 is single shot detection. It is characterized by being very efficient while maintaining a comparable accuracy to the state-of-the-art networks of its time.

First of all, SSD makes use of two key ideas that grant it its characteristics:

- Multiple convolutional feature maps encode information at different scales.
- Collection of different filters that specialize in predicting boxes in different sizes.

In figure 2.2, a typical SSD architecture workflow can be seen. The process can be separated into approximately three stages: Feature extraction, Detection, and Non-max suppression [1].

The feature extraction stage is responsible for generating feature maps. Like with depthwise separable convolutions, this means that it extracts valuable information from the image. For instance, feature maps can give an insight into how edges are oriented or where they are located. A standard architecture for high-quality image classification is used to achieve this extraction, but it is truncated before any classification layer. Furthermore, convolutional feature layers of progressively decreasing size are appended to the shortened image classification network [Liu+16]. These allow the network to output multiple feature maps of different sizes and thus make predictions of detections at different scales.

The detection stage is responsible for generating the actual bounding box predictions and class confidence scores. These are obtained from the different-sized feature maps from the previous stage. The idea is that each feature map cell has a fixed set of default bounding boxes. Consequently, each feature layer from the previous stage can generate a fixed set of detection predictions related to these default boxes. This is done using convolutional filters that have varying sizes depending on the connected feature layer. For a feature layer of size $m \times n$ with p channels, we need a kernel of size $3 \times 3 \times p$ that will be shifted around the $m \times n$ possible locations. This means that the default boxes divide the image in a convolutional manner and vary in size and offset depending on the feature map they are applied to [Liu+16]. Furthermore, the detector predicts for every default box if the content inside corresponds to an object. In particular, a default box will have two parameters associated with it:

- The class confidence score indicates what and how accurately an object was detected. If there are several possibilities, the class with the highest score is kept for this particular default box.

- The box offset prediction concerns the relative positioning of the object to the default box. To illustrate this, consider a default bounding box. It has a specific size, position and aspect ratio, which in most cases does not perfectly fit the entire object. The box offset predictions adjust this default bounding box coordinates to hold the object better, thus making the detection area more accurate.

To summarise, these parameters will be computed for every default bounding box in every feature map cell, and we call a box positive if an object has been detected inside of it. [Liu+16]

Figure 2.3 shows the detection process in a simplified way. In figure 2.3a, a default bounding box can be observed before it slides over the insect. It is not detecting an object and is thus counted as a negative box. In figure 2.3b, we can see that the same box is now shifted over the insect, detecting an object and consequently being considered a positive box. Finally, figure 2.3c shows a different default bounding box that will never yield a detection for this image because of its aspect ratio. As a result, it is counted as a negative box.

(a) Default bounding box of type 1 with- (b) Default bounding box of type 1 with (c) Default bounding box of a different
out detection. detection. type.

Figure 2.3: Example single shot detections at different scales with varying sized default bounding boxes.

The Non-Maximal Suppression stage functions as post-processing in the network and will produce the actual predictions [1]. The former stage outputs data (class confidence and box offset) for every default bounding box, and the goal is here to filter out unnecessary information. First of all, only positive boxes will be considered since these are the ones that contain actual objects. Furthermore, multiple positive boxes can detect the same object because of the different-sized feature maps. The IoU is used to differentiate overlapping boxes in this case. IoU stands for Intersection over Union and can be calculated by dividing the intersection area by the total area of the overlapping boxes [2]. For all boxes that have an $IoU > 0.5$, only the box with the highest confidence score is kept while the other ones are discarded [1]. This ensures that only the best detections are preserved.

So what is responsible for the performance increase? At the time, most non-SSD models relied on bounding box proposals and the following feature resampling stage. These methods are not needed in SSD models and eliminating them represents the biggest speed increase. However, what sets SSD apart from other performance-oriented architectures is that detections are being made at different scales, which significantly improves the accuracy of the network while retaining the speed increase. [Liu+16]

2.1.3 Combined network architecture

The basic principles that characterize SSD and Mobilenetv1/v2 models have been investigated separately. However, the model used in this thesis combines both concepts. SSD networks use truncated classification models in their feature extraction stage. Previously, VGG16 was used for this. However, it is large and can exceed the maximum system memory

of an embedded platform [Chi+20]. To solve this, VGG16 was replaced with the Mobilenet-v2 network. This allowed the entire network to achieve real-time performance [3].

2.2 Tensorflow Object Detection API

Computer Vision applications are on the rise, and modern applications require more efficient models. However, another important goal is facilitating their development, training and evaluation. With more and more use cases appearing every day, these processes' simplicity and speed become increasingly important [NST19, p.1]. This gave birth to machine learning frameworks like Pytorch or Tensorflow that facilitate these tasks. The training framework chosen for this thesis is Tensorflow's Object Detection API which will be investigated in this section.

2.2.1 General

"Tensorflow is an end-to-end open-source platform for machine learning"[4]. It is developed by Google and features multiple libraries and tools that cover different needs for machine learning applications. Tensorflow mainly supports APIs in Python and C++ but also offers a backwards-compatible API for other languages.

Tensorflow's Object Detection API is a framework built on Tensorflow that specializes in Object Detection. Its goal is to simplify the use and training of Object Detection models [NST19, p.1]. This is achieved in several ways that will be examined now.

2.2.2 Pre-trained models

First of all, Tensorflow offers many pre-trained Detection models in its "Detection Model Zoo" on GitHub [5]. These are based on different architectures and are all listed in a table with their respective speed (in ms) and accuracy (in mAP). The models have all been trained on the COCO 2017 dataset, which features 91 common object categories on about 330 000 images [Lin+14] and is commonly used to train computer vision models. Tensorflow has provided these networks to allow users "out-of-the-box inference" [5] meaning that the user can choose a model and run inference quickly without the need to implement or train anything. An "SSD Mobilenet-v2 320x320" can be found in this model zoo which will serve as the base network for this thesis.

2.2.3 Model storage

This raises the question of how models are stored in Tensorflow. They are composed of different files grouped in a model folder [6]. This folder contains:

- The "checkpoint" folder is a directory containing training checkpoints. The latter store the exact value of all parameters the model uses at a particular time. However, no description of computation is included.
- The "saved_model" folder is a directory consisting of serialized signatures and the state needed to run them. Specifically, this folder contains a "saved_model.pb" file that stores the actual model with a set of named signatures. These signatures each identify a function that accepts a tensor as input and produces a tensor as output. Furthermore, this folder includes a "variables" directory containing a default checkpoint and an optional "assets" directory that would consist of files used by the Tensorflow Graph.

- The "pipeline.config" file is a protobuf file used to configure the training and evaluation process. It can be split into five sections: model configuration, training configuration, evaluation configuration, training input and evaluation input.

2.2.4 Training

Even though Tensorflow gives access to many pre-trained detection models, the user might want to train the model with custom data. Whether one wants to train a model from scratch or further expand a pre-trained one, the process is roughly the same. First, the custom dataset needs to be prepared. For detection models, the data will be found in images and associated annotation files that contain the coordinates of the detection bounding boxes. However, Tensorflow accepts training and evaluation data as TFRecord files. These files store data as a sequence of binary strings [6]. Consequently, this format speeds up the training and evaluation process, but the user will need to convert our annotations and images into the TFRecord format. After completing this, a "pipeline.config" file needs to be set up. Here parameters like the learning rate in the "training configuration" section can be adjusted, or the file paths pointing to the training files in the "training input" section can be added. Section 4 will go into more detail about the "pipeline.config" file configuration. The training process can be started with a python training script that Tensorflow provides on their GitHub page. However, a custom training script can be written using Tensorflow's API documentation. During training, Tensorflow will periodically write new checkpoints into the checkpoint folder. These serve as saved states at a certain point in time. This is useful if the training job is cancelled; the training can continue at the last checkpoint where it was aborted. The periodicity of when these checkpoints are written can be set up during the training job launch or inside the training script. [6]

Another aspect of training that Tensorflow facilitates and is relevant for this thesis is image augmentation methods. Image augmentation refers to randomly applying transformations to the training data to create an extra layer of variance. This should make the model more general and thus perform better [7]. These methods range from colour operations to geometric operations (geometrically distorting the image) to bounding box operations (only pixel content in the bounding box distorted). Of course, which methods to apply depends on the actual use case, but if done correctly, a performance increase of about 2% has been measured on PASCAL VOC and COCO datasets. This might be favourable in comparison to changing the detection model because the performance increase due to image augmentation presents no additional inference cost and minimal training investment [Zop+20]. Tensorflow offers a large number of augmentation methods. The user must add some lines in the "pipeline.config" file to use them. The framework will then automatically add transformed images and annotations to the training data [7].

2.2.5 Evaluation

Tensorflow also provides tools to facilitate and streamline the evaluation process of machine learning models. First of all, there are two different points in time one can evaluate the model with Tensorflow: during training and after training [6]. Model evaluation during training is called Validation. The training script mentioned in the section 2.2.4 launches the validation job in parallel with the training job. The validation job waits for checkpoints that the training job creates and uses them one by one to test the model's performance at this particular time on a separate dataset specified with the file location in the "pipeline.config" file [7]. Evaluation after training is called testing. Like with training, Tensorflow provides testing scripts to run inference and measure the model performance, or a custom script can be written using Tensorflow's API documentation. Additionally, Tensorflow will write model-performance and

optimizer state-related logs using the TFEvents format. This data is created during a training or evaluation job in the model folder. To visualize these results, the framework includes an easy-to-use but powerful performance tracking tool called "Tensorboard". [6]

2.3 OpenVINO

The second framework presented and used for inference in this thesis is OpenVINO. OpenVINO stands for Open Visual Inference and Neural Network Optimization toolkit and was developed by Intel. It was created to facilitate the workflow of machine learning applications and also provide tools to optimize these applications for different Intel hardware [8]. The supported hardware at the time of the thesis is:

- Intel CPUs
- Intel Processor Graphics
- Intel Neural Compute Stick 2
- Intel Vision Accelerator Design with Intel Movidius VPUs

The OpenVINO workflow will now be examined to understand its use in this thesis.

2.3.1 Model preparation

The first step is to choose one or several models. Similarly to Tensorflow, OpenVINO provides a collection of pre-trained models in their "Open Model Zoo" [9]. These cover a variety of machine learning tasks like text recognition, object detection or facial recognition. Acquiring these models can be done in different ways. They can either be downloaded with OpenVINO's "Model Downloader" tool that is provided with the toolkit or directly from the GitHub page. However, OpenVINO also supports other machine learning frameworks like Pytorch or Tensorflow, which is relevant for this thesis. [8]

2.3.2 Model storage and conversion

OpenVINO features its format of operation sets and graph representation to store machine learning models. It is called "Intermediate Representation" or "IR". A saved model in this Intermediate Representation consists of 2 files:

- A .xml file describes the network topology using .xml tags. For instance it uses "<layer>" tags to define operation nodes or "<edge>" tags to define data-flow connections.
- A binary file stores constant values like convolution weights in a binary format.

These files work together to create a computable model for OpenVINO's Inference Engine. To illustrate this, consider that the .xml file does not store constant values like the convolution weights. It rather points to the associated part of the accompanying binary file [8]. These files can then be used to run OpenVINO's inference.

In many cases, including the one for this thesis, the starting model will be provided in a different framework like Tensorflow. OpenVINO provides a "Model Optimizer" for this case. Latter is a cross-platform command-line tool that converts our model from a supported source framework into the Intermediate Representation. There are a lot of supported source

frameworks like Caffe, Tensorflow, Kaldi, MXNet and ONNX. However, since OpenVINO features its own operation sets that depend on the source framework, usage of the model optimizer also varies in terms of parameters the user needs to set and how well the conversion represents the original network. [8]

2.3.3 Inference

After the model has been converted into the Intermediate Representation format, it is ready for inference. OpenVINO provides the Inference Engine for this purpose. Latter is a set of C++ libraries with an API in C, C++ and Python. The Inference Engine accepts models in IR or ONNX format and will execute the model optimally for a specific piece of Intel hardware [8]. In the paper, [And20, p.4], Tensorflow and OpenVino Inference are compared side by side with an SSD Mobilenet-v2 from the OpenVINO Model Downloader on an Intel (R) Core i5-4460 CPU @3.20HZ with four cores allocated to a virtual machine running the inference. Concerning precision, Tensorflow and OpenVINO are identical. They both recognize the same amount of objects with the same precision. However, the average gain in the number of frames per second for OpenVINO Inference is 126.4 times. This represents a significant performance improvement. On the other hand, OpenVINO inhibits a higher standard deviation of performance than Tensorflow. Tensorflow varies with a standard deviation of 0.0026 frames per second, while OpenVINO varies with 3.9886 frames per second. Despite this, no dependence on the number of objects in the image and the performance deviation can be observed. Overall, since the average gain in frames is so significant, the usage of OpenVINO is still vastly justified.

2.3.4 Tuning for performance

In addition to the Inference Engine, OpenVINO's Toolkit also provides tools for measuring performance to tune the model. First, measurement tools like the "Accuracy Checker" can be found. This command-line application is used to validate model performance and can be set up in different ways with the help of a config file [8].

OpenVINO provides tools for calibrating the model after training if the model's performance is unsatisfactory. These are summarized in the Post-Training Optimization tool (POT). Latter is designed to accelerate inference without retraining or fine-tuning the model. It features a command-line interface and a Python API to allow easy integration into custom applications. The POT requires an IR model and a representative subset of the dataset that the model has been trained with [8]. It will then apply techniques like post-training quantization, tailored compression for different hardware, symmetric or asymmetric quantization schemes or per channel quantization for Convolutional or Fully-Connected layers to enhance the model's performance. The POT offers two calibration methods: Default and AccuracyAware. The Default mode produces the fastest model while generally lowering the accuracy by 1%. On the other hand, AccuracyAware mode creates an optimized model tuned for the best performance possible while holding a specified maximum acceptable accuracy drop [Dem+20, p. 664].

2.3.5 Packaging and deployment

Finally, the last aspect that makes OpenVINO very useful is that it offers a tool for packaging and deploying machine learning applications. The tool is called the "Deployment Manager" and is a Python command-line tool. It assembles the model, IR files, the application and associated dependencies into a runtime package for a selectable target device [8]. This deployment tool seems trivial compared to other tasks like training or testing. However, it is handy because it allows the user to quickly wrap and ship the application to a different system with all the necessary files. This is often

an underestimated aspect of model development for a specific target system and presents a welcome addition to the overall toolkit [Dem+20, p. 664].

2.4 Dataset

This use case aims to recognize pedestrians in traffic situations; consequently, the data should reflect that. Therefore, the dataset comprises three parts assembled by combining three different datasets that all picture traffic situations with annotated pedestrians.

2.4.1 PETS2009

Figure 2.4: PETS09 dataset organization

The first part is the PETS2009 dataset from the PETS (Performance Evaluation of Tracking and Surveillance) workshop. This workshop aimed to test new and existing detection systems within a real-world environment. This was achieved by setting a challenge and providing a unified dataset for all participants. Since then, PETS2009 has been used for numerous research projects. The images have been taken at Whiteknights Campus at the University of Reading in the United Kingdom [FS09]. The staged traffic situations were captured by eight cameras and showed up to 40 individuals at a time.

The general organization of the dataset can be seen in Figure 2.4. As can be seen, it is roughly composed of 4 parts. Each of these parts is again divided into subsets and contains several sequences of pictures where each sequence is taken from different views (camera position). The reason for this organization is that the various parts fulfil different purposes for the challenge. For instance, the pictures in S1L1 will show a walking medium-density crowd, and the challenge's goal was to count the number of people. On the other hand, the images in S2L1 will show a sparse crowd, and the challenge's goal was to track the people. [10] However, this thesis did not use the entire dataset. The focus remained on one view, and a few sequences from S1L1, S2L1, S2L2, S2L3, and S3MF were selected from the whole subset. Figure 2.5 shows two selected sample images from the dataset taken from PETS2009.

Figure 2.5: Example pictures of PETS dataset

2.4.2 TownCentre

The second part is the TownCentre dataset. This dataset is a 5 min CCTV video filming pedestrians in a busy downtown area in Oxford, United Kingdom. It was published in 2009 and has been used in more than 60 verified research projects. Its primary purpose was to enable the research and development of pedestrian detection and tracking as well as facial recognition systems [BR11]. This dataset is unique because it uses unposed footage from a public surveillance camera, making the data more realistic [11]. The dataset comprises 7500 annotated frames, but in this thesis, we used a total of 3089. Figure 2.6 shows a sample image from the dataset taken from TownCentre.

Figure 2.6: Example picture of TownCentre dataset

2.4.3 TUD-Stadtmitte

The last part of the dataset is the TUD-Stadtmitte dataset. It is part of several datasets like "TUD Multiview pedestrians" or "TUD Crossings" and was created by the Technical University in Darmstadt, Germany. These datasets were primarily used to investigate single-frame people detection, and viewpoint estimations [ARS10]. However, it has also been used for other applications like multiple objects tracking [WX16]. Figure 2.7 shows a sample image from the dataset taken from TUD-Stadtmitte. As can be seen, the picture is taken from a street-level view of Darmstadt's town centre. This should make the total data more diverse because the previous two datasets show that the photographs were taken from a higher angle. A total of 180 images from TownCentre have been used for this thesis.

Figure 2.7: Example picture of TUD-Stadtmitte dataset

Chapter 3

Data preprocessing

Now that the principles on which this thesis is built have been explored, it is time to turn the attention to the necessary steps to conduct the experiments. The first part was the preparation of the dataset.

As section 2.4 has shown, the dataset is composed of 3 different subsets. The goal was to harmonize this data and create the desired TFRecords format mentioned in section 2.2.4.

3.1 Annotations

First, it is important to talk about the annotation format in which these datasets were distributed. Starting with the PETS09, this dataset was distributed in CVML format. This stands for Computer Vision Markup Language and is an old and outdated format. It was introduced in 2004 to harmonise image annotation formats to enable simpler cooperation between research teams. The format dictates that an annotated sequence is composed of the actual frames (or images) and an accompanying annotation file in .xml format. This file contains all the necessary information for computer vision tasks. For instance, it will inhibit all detections with the exact coordinates in pixels. Listing 3.1.a shows an example of the structure of the CVML annotations for the PETS09 dataset. As can be seen, the annotation file presents the typical .xml hierarchical structure denoting all detections for each frame. It is important to note that CVML does not dictate the exact structure of the annotations but serves as a guideline. This means there can be small variances in the organization depending on the case. [LF04]

Next, the TownCentre dataset was received in PASCAL VOC format. This standard annotation format originated from the Pattern Analysis, Statistical Modelling and Computational Learning Visual Object Challenge (PASCAL VOC). This challenge provided a standardized dataset to test and compare the capabilities of detection and classification models. The delivered dataset was annotated in a unified way called PASCAL VOC today. The annotations are again stored in a .xml file. Still, there are two significant differences compared to CVML: PASCAL VOC has stricter structuring rules than CVML, and every image has its annotation file. Listing 3.1.b shows an example annotation file from the provided TownCentre dataset. As can be observed, there is more information on the particular image and the information is structured differently. For instance, the bounding boxes are presented with exact coordinates rather than a width and height. [Eve+10]

```

1     <dataset name="PETS-S1L1-1">
2       <frame number="0">
3         <objectlist>
4           <object id="1">
5             <box h="105.1412" w="51.9479" xc="630.1302" yc="310.6886"/>
6           </object>
7           <object id="2">
8             <box h="108.4689" w="53.5932" xc="687.2705" yc="322.8721"/>
9           </object>
10          <object id="3">
11            <box h="53.8528" w="22.954" xc="57.56" yc="168.3829"/>
12          </object>
13          <object id="4">
14            <box h="108.2209" w="42.468" xc="705.028" yc="281.3549"/>
15          </object>
16          <object id="5">
17            <box h="98.8127" w="40.9666" xc="691.7807" yc="313.8245"/>
18          </object>
19        </objectlist>
20      </frame>

```

(a) CVML .xml file

```

1     <annotation>
2       <filename>TownCentre_frame_0799.jpg</filename>
3       <size>
4         <width>960</width>
5         <height>540</height>
6         <depth>3</depth>
7       </size>
8       <object>
9         <name>pedestrian</name>
10        <bndbox>
11          <xmin>859</xmin>
12          <ymin>7</ymin>
13          <xmax>893</xmax>
14          <ymax>79</ymax>
15        </bndbox>
16      </object>
17      <object>
18        <name>pedestrian</name>
19        <bndbox>
20          <xmin>515</xmin>
21          <ymin>26</ymin>
22          <xmax>539</xmax>
23          <ymax>97</ymax>
24        </bndbox>
25      </object>

```

(b) PASCAL VOC .xml file

```

1     1, -1, 428, 98, 104, 236, 117.87, 4.13165, 1.86548, 0
2     1, -1, 332, 82, 104, 236, 108.56, 5.13248, 3.32803, 0
3     1, -1, 172, 82, 104, 236, 86.876, 4.74369, 4.61071, 0
4     1, -1, 84, 104, 94.545, 214.55, 64.757, 4.45954, 5.34498, 0
5     1, -1, 557, 82, 86.667, 196.67, 57.068, 9.38632, 3.51115, 0
6     1, -1, 506, 115, 56.877, 129.07, 52.409, 14.3846, 6.96685, 0
7     2, -1, 428, 98, 104, 236, 116.05, 4.13165, 1.86548, 0
8     2, -1, 332, 82, 104, 236, 99.034, 5.13248, 3.32803, 0
9     2, -1, 172, 82, 104, 236, 97.914, 4.74369, 4.61071, 0
10    2, -1, 69, 104, 94.545, 214.55, 90.341, 4.40947, 5.46301, 0
11    2, -1, 563, 88, 80, 181.54, 58.216, 10.5301, 4.05489, 0
12    2, -1, 506, 115, 56.877, 129.07, 56.975, 14.3846, 6.96685, 0

```

(c) YOLO-like .txt file

Listing 3.1: Different annotation file excerpts

Finally, the TUD-Stadtmitte dataset was distributed in a YOLO-like format. The format was introduced when the first YOLO (You Only Look Once) neural network was published. Annotations are stored in .txt files, and each image will have a corresponding .txt file that lists all detections on separate lines. [Red+16] Listing 3.1.c shows an example of a YOLO-like annotation file from the TUD-Stadtmitte dataset. First, different detections are placed on various file lines, giving the file a YOLO-like characteristic. Second, the file contains annotations for multiple images, which differs from the standard YOLO format.

3.2 Conversion

As mentioned in section 2.2.4, the training framework Tensorflow does not accept training data in CVML, PASCAL VOC or YOLO format but in the form of TFRecords files. The necessity of this target format inherently means a conversion was needed. This can be done in several ways, but the task has been tackled as presented in figure 3.1. The main idea is to use the widespread COCO detection data format. Latter originated from the COCO dataset and is widely used today as a standard to store annotations [Lin+14]. Consequently, a wide selection of converters transforms data from COCO to TFRecords, saving unnecessary work. In summary, the source format will first be transformed into a .csv file, then into the COCO data format, which can easily be converted into TFRecord files. This raises the question of how annotation data is stored in COCO format.

Figure 3.1: Annotation file conversion workflow

First, the COCO format stores annotations in a .json file and all classes in an accompanying .txt file. The .json file inhibits a software object-like structure. Different pieces of information are stored with attributes which allow strong categorization of the contained information. Furthermore, COCO annotation files preserve all annotations for the entire dataset in one file where each image file is specified inside. Another point that should be mentioned is that the bounding boxes are stored with absolute coordinates of the bottom left corner along with the width and height.

To achieve the conversion, python converter scripts had to be created that transform CVML and YOLO-like annotations into COCO annotations. Python was chosen as a development language because it is easy to use, the training framework Tensorflow supports a Python API, and many libraries for different related tasks are available.

As seen in section 3.1, CVML consists of .xml files that are structured like in listing 3.1.a. The data must be saved into a .csv file to obtain a COCO .json file. This was the first script that needed to be written. The basic flow of the script can be seen in figure 3.2. First, the .xml data was saved into a dictionary using a python library. This reads the .xml file, categorizes the data in a python dictionary, and makes single data entries easily accessible. While iterating through every frame of the dictionary, all the detection data was extracted and written into a python array entry. One thing to mention here again is that the COCO format dictates that bounding box detections are stored in the following manner

$(x_{min}, y_{min}, width, height)$. In other words, COCO stores the exact coordinate of the bottom left corner of the bounding box along with the width and height. In CVML, bounding boxes are stored with the exact coordinate of the centre of the bottom edge of the bounding box along with the width and height, meaning $(x_{centre}, y_{centre}, width, height)$. This meant two important things that needed to be considered. First, the right computation and storage needed to be in place. At this stage, computing $(x_{min}, y_{min}, x_{max}, y_{max})$ will suffice for further processing. Furthermore, let us consider if a detection is near the left edge of the image. The bottom left coordinate can be calculated with:

$$x_{min} = x_{center} - \frac{width}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

However, an $x_{center} < \frac{width}{2}$ will yield $x_{min} < 0$. This means x_{min} should be set to 0 in this case. The same logic applies vice versa to the maximum values:

$$x_{max} = x_{center} + \frac{width}{2} \quad (3.2)$$

$x_{center} > x_{resolution} - \frac{width}{2}$ will yield $x_{max} > x_{resolution}$ where $x_{resolution}$ is the width of the image. x_{max} should be set to $x_{resolution}$ in this case. Consequently, this problem also applies to the y direction.

After a complete iteration through the entire dictionary, the array was filled with the correct data. The former could then be transformed into a dataframe from where a .csv file was easily computable using the pandas python library.

Figure 3.2: Flow diagram of .xml to .csv conversion

Next, the .csv file needed to be converted into a COCO annotation .json file. To achieve this, a second script was written that converts .csv files to COCO .json files. The basic flow of the script can be observed in figure 3.3. First, the .csv data was read into a dataframe. Then a .txt file containing all classes was created. This might be trivial for this use case

since there is just one class (pedestrian). Nevertheless, a more flexible approach was chosen to reuse the script for other datasets containing more than one class. Therefore, the different classes were stored in an array by iterating through the rows of the dataframe while extracting the class of every detection. A new class was appended if it was not already contained in the array. Next, the classes were written into a .txt file. For the creation of the .json file, a software object was produced and initialized with attributes according to COCO annotations. While iterating through the dataframe, the data was extracted and assigned to the right attributes of the software object. Note that it was here that the final necessary computations like calculating *width*, *height* or the *area* took place. Finally, the now populated data object was written into a .json file using the JSON python library.

Figure 3.3: Flow diagram of .csv to COCO conversion

The CVML conversion was reused for the YOLO-like conversion to save time and effort. If the YOLO-like data is written to a .csv file with the same structure as before, the .csv to COCO script can be reused. Consequently, only a script was needed that transforms the YOLO-like data into a .csv file. Figure 3.4 shows the basic flow of this script. It is very similar to the CVML .xml to .csv conversion. First, the source.txt file was read with python's native file handler. While iterating over the rows of the file, the content was extracted into a string. From there, the data was extracted by splitting the

latter. Next, the exact coordinates were computed as before, and the necessary data was written into an array. This array was then converted into a dataframe which was transformed into a .csv file.

Figure 3.4: Flow diagram of .txt to .csv conversion

After harmonizing the annotations of the entire dataset into the COCO format, existing software could be used to convert from COCO to TFRecords.

3.3 Partitioning

Figure 3.5: Partitioning of dataset

Figure 3.5 shows the partitioning of the dataset. A total of 5641 annotated images were split with an 80/20% ratio where all subsets were equally represented in both test and train sets. This means that, for instance, the ratio of images from TownCentre in the train set is equal to the ratio of images from TownCentre in the test set. This ensured a fairer comparison when testing. Furthermore, not all images or sequences from the respective subsets have been included.

The training set was composed of:

- PETS09_S1L1_t1357_view001
- PETS09_S1L2_t1406_view001
- PETS09_S2L1_t1234_view001
- PETS09_S2L2_t1455_view001
- PETS09_S2L3_t1441_view001
- TownCentre 0-2499
- TUD-StadtMitte 0-139

The test set was composed of:

- PETS09_S1L1_t1359_view001
- PETS09_S1L2_t1431_view001
- PETS09_S3MF_t1243_view001
- TownCentre 2500-3089
- TUD-StadtMitte 140-179

First, the images from TownCentre and TUD-Stadtmitte were split by dividing the frames with the specified ratio since these are just relatively short videos. As discussed in section 2.4, not all sequences from the PETS09 dataset have been included. Figure 3.6, shows a sample of all included sequences. As can be seen, all scenarios were taken from the same elevated viewpoint. The difference between them lies in the staged traffic situation. For example, figures 3.6c and 3.6e show a variance in crowd density and movement (denoted by "S2L1"). Moreover, the shooting period of the sequence varies as well (denoted by "t1234"). For this reason, the test set also included a broad time range and footage from sparse and crowded sequences.

The same test set for the evaluation during training was used for the inference on the target devices to keep things simple.

Figure 3.6: Sample of included sequences from PETS dataset

Chapter 4

Experiment setup

Now that the data is harmonized, fused, split and ready to use, it is time to look at how the training environment, the measurement environment and the experiments have been laid out.

4.1 Training setup

First, all training has been done on a server with two Tesla V100 graphic cards from the ICT institute. On this server, a workspace was created that contained all necessary files for training and served as a place to conduct all training-related tasks.

As mentioned in section 2.1 and 2.2.2, the base network for this thesis is an SSD Mobilenet-v2. This model has been taken from Tensorflow’s Model Zoo and was pre-trained on the COCO dataset [5]. However, slight changes have been made to the standard parameters of our base network to have a better starting point. A summary of the base parameters compared to the original model can be observed in table 4.1. First, the resolution has been set from 320×320 pixels to 768×576 pixels because this corresponds to the image resolution of the PETS images. Next, the number of classes has decreased to 1 since the model only needs to detect pedestrians and the dataset only has one class. Furthermore, it is also essential to consider that the base network uses a momentum optimizer and a cosine decay learning rate schedule with a warmup. The learning rate was reduced to 0.08 and the warmup learning rate to 0.01 because an initial test run with the base learning rates yielded unusable results and, therefore, a bad starting point. Furthermore, the batch size has been decreased to 32 because the server cannot run a training with a batch size of 512. Finally, the number of training steps has been increased to 60000, and the number of warmup training steps has been raised from 2000 to 2400. This was done to compensate for the inferior batch size and preserve the original ratio of warmup training steps to total training steps. The rest of the parameters remained unchanged. It should also be noted that the base setup of Tensorflow’s Object Detection API incorporates two image augmentation methods. These are a random image flip and a random image crop.

Model	Resolution	Batch size	Learning rate	Warmup learning rate	Number of steps
Original	320x320	512	0.8	0.1	50 000
Base	768x576	32	0.08	0.01	60 000

Table 4.1: Summary comparison of original and adapted base SSD Mobilenet-v2

As seen in section 2.2.4, the config file from the network needs to be edited to change any of these parameters. Listing 4.1 shows the training setup part of this file type, where several needed changes can be observed. Some of the before-mentioned parameters that have been changed are shown by the orange highlighted lines. Furthermore, the green highlighted lines showcase the network's previously mentioned base data augmentation options. Section 4.3.4 will go into more detail on augmentation parameters. Finally, several paths needed to be configured for the model, which is highlighted in blue.

```

1      train_config {
2          batch_size: 32
3          data_augmentation_options {
4              random_horizontal_flip {
5              }
6          }
7          data_augmentation_options {
8              ssd_random_crop {
9              }
10         }
11         sync_replicas: true
12         optimizer {
13             momentum_optimizer {
14                 learning_rate {
15                     cosine_decay_learning_rate {
16                         learning_rate_base: 0.08
17                         total_steps: 60000
18                         warmup_learning_rate: 0.01
19                         warmup_steps: 2400
20                     }
21                 }
22                 momentum_optimizer_value: 0.8999999761581421
23             }
24             use_moving_average: false
25         }
26         fine_tune_checkpoint: "PATH_TO_BE_CONFIGURED"
27         num_steps: 60000
28         startup_delay_steps: 0.0
29         replicas_to_aggregate: 8
30         max_number_of_boxes: 100
31         unpad_groundtruth_tensors: false
32         fine_tune_checkpoint_type: "detection"
33         fine_tune_checkpoint_version: V2
34     }
35     train_input_reader {
36         label_map_path: "PATH_TO_BE_CONFIGURED"
37         tf_record_input_reader {
38             input_path: "PATH_TO_BE_CONFIGURED"
39         }
40     }
41     eval_config {
42         metrics_set: "coco_detection_metrics"
43         use_moving_averages: false
44     }
45     eval_input_reader {
46         label_map_path: "PATH_TO_BE_CONFIGURED"
47         shuffle: false
48         num_epochs: 1
49         tf_record_input_reader {
50             input_path: "PATH_TO_BE_CONFIGURED"
51         }
52     }

```

Listing 4.1: Training setup of a base pipeline.config file

Consequently, config files play a significant role because they define the parameters that will guide the training process and thus determine how the network will be trained. This means that for every version of the network, a dedicated config file with the necessary parameters was created based on the training setup of Listing 4.1.

After a config file was created, it was moved inside the workspace. A shell script template was created for the actual training that trains, evaluates and exports a model. The template uses different scripts provided by Tensorflow that are being run one after the other. One could ask what exporting a model means because one could copy and paste the model folder after the training is done. As seen in section 2.2.4, the training script periodically writes checkpoints into the model folder during the training process. These checkpoints require storage space, and not every single one was needed for the actual inference since they are only saved network states at a particular time. Exporting outputs a new model folder with the minimum content inside of it, which was used for most models. At the same time, for some experiments and models, the training process should be recorded for further observations. This meant that the checkpoints were kept for specific models to examine the performance changes during the training process. This required a separate shell script. With these templates, an accompanying training script to a config file could be created, and the different variations of the SSD Mobilenet-v2 with custom parameters could be trained.

4.2 Measurement setup

First, since it is a central topic of the thesis, almost all measurements have been done on an Intel-NUC computer, except the measurements recorded during model training. Table 4.2 shows a summary of its specifications. It features a CPU and a GPU, and measurements have been conducted on both devices. Moreover, the networks were also tested on an Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2) plugged into the NUC via USB. This stick does not have a CPU or GPU but operates using Intel’s Movidius Myriad Vision Processing Unit (VPU). Its specifications can be observed in table 4.3.

Attribute	Value
Full name	Intel NUC NUC7i7DNK2E
CPU	i7-8650U 4 Cores 8 Threads
GPU	Intel HD 620
TDP [W]	15
Cooling	Active

Table 4.2: Hardware specification of Intel-NUC

Attribute	Value
Full name	Intel Neural Compute Stick 2
VPU	Intel Movidius Myriad VPU
TDP [W]	1,5-3
Cooling	Passive

Table 4.3: Hardware specification of Intel NCS2

Just like in section 4.1, a workspace was created on the Intel-NUC for this thesis that contained all necessary files and served as a space to conduct all measurements. The latter consisted of recording the two metrics mentioned in section 1.3:

- Mean latency represents a model’s average time to infer one image.
- Mean average precision (mAP) characterizes the accuracy of a model. This metric represents the mean value of the Average Precision (AP) of a model. There are different levels of calculating this metric depending on the IoU that is set. For our experiments, we focused on an mAP value at 0.50 IoU.

As discussed in section 2.3.2, the trained models need to be converted to OpenVino’s Intermediate Representation format

with the help of the Model Optimizer for the Inference with OpenVino. After placing an exported Tensorflow model into the workspace, a conversion script was used to convert the Tensorflow model into an IR model. For every Tensorflow model, 2 IR versions were created: a quantized 16-Bit floating point and a 32-Bit floating point version. However, we have to consider that only the GPU can process both 16- and 32-Bit floating-point operations. The CPU can only support 32-Bit and the NCS2 16-Bit operations. This means both versions will only be tested on the GPU.

At this point, the models were ready for the Inference with OpenVino, but a few more steps were needed to measure comfortably. Notably, a system was missing that automatically infers all images of the test set while extracting the necessary metrics after the inference of one image is done. A template script for inferring, evaluating and storing the results was built to achieve this with the help of the OpenVino API documentation. The main part of the template was about running Open Vino Inference with a model and extracting the detections into a .csv file. Figure 4.1 showcases the workflow of this. Starting by loading the model, an iteration over all test images was needed. For every iteration, an image is loaded, and the inference is run. Then the detection data is extracted and written into an array. After completing the necessary tasks over the entire test set, the array is converted to a dataframe, which is then transformed into a .csv file.

Figure 4.1: Flow diagram of OpenVino result parser

With the help of scripts provided by the ICT institute and all the previously mentioned tools, inference and measurements could be automated, thus saving time. It is important to note that three devices have been tested on the Intel-NUC: CPU, GPU and the NCS2. The target metrics were computed, and the results were written into a .csv file.

4.3 Experiments

The examination was structured into separate experiments with a dedicated central research question.

4.3.1 Dataset and subsets

The first experiment is about the dataset and its subsets. The central question is: Is it better to train the model only on the PETS09 subset or the entire dataset?

Four different variations were trained to answer this question. The training and validation sets were changed according to table 4.4. For instance, the first network only used the PETS09 data as a training and validation set. The remaining parameters stayed the same as the base model.

Training	Validation
PETS	PETS
PETS	All
All	PETS
All	All

Table 4.4: Subset variations

A test and validation subset of our PETS09 data were created to conduct this experiment. Afterwards, a dedicated conversion to the TFRecords format of the latter was necessary. Next, the data needed to be moved into the training workspace. Then it was time to create different config files based on the initial model described in section 4.1.

After training, the exported models were moved to the measurement workspace on the Intel-NUC. From there, the models were converted and inferred with the test set to obtain the measurements.

The reason for choosing the PETS09 set as a constant factor is because it features a significant amount of images. Therefore, a precision increase is expected when training on more data. Additionally, the other subsets feature different viewpoints and traffic situations and eliminating them could cause a notable performance dip. Finally, only a difference in latency can be predicted between the different devices, while the precision should stay device independent.

4.3.2 Learning rate

The second experiment was about the learning rate, and the research question was: For this dataset, a batch size of 32 and a training duration of 60000 steps, what is the best learning rate?

ID	Learning rate	Warmup learning rate
1	0.8	0.1
2	0.08	0.01
3	0.008	0.001
4	0.0008	0.0001
5	0.00008	0.00001
6	0.000008	0.000001

Table 4.5: Learning & warmup learning rate variations

Different network variations were trained to examine this topic while changing the learning rate in powers of ten. Since the warmup learning rate is not allowed to be larger than the learning rate, the latter also needed to be changed. Table 4.5 presents these variations. The remaining parameters stayed the same as the base network, but the network was trained on the entire dataset this time.

As seen in section 4.1, the network features a cosine decay learning rate schedule. This means the learning rate will

increase to the maximum value and gradually decrease during training. Therefore a performance decline can be expected for lower learning rates.

4.3.3 Learning rate and training steps

The main question of the following experiment is: How many epochs should be trained for this dataset and a batch size of 32? The central theme is thus the relation between learning rate and the number of training steps.

An examination of the change in performance during the training process was needed while varying the learning rate for the network variations. First, the number of training steps has been increased to 300 000 for all models. During training, a checkpoint of the model was saved every 10 000 steps. This allowed the computation of the mAP for these points in time. A 30-measurement record of the training process was the result.

The investigation was split into two parts. First, regular variations of the base network were initiated while the learning rate was altered like in section 4.3.2 meaning in powers of ten. Second, a representative subset of our total dataset was created featuring 20% of the training images while respecting the ratio of the in section 3.3 mentioned subsets. This was then used as a training set for other base network variations with altered learning rates. The focus was to measure a difference in performance due to the number of training steps, the learning rate and the number of training images. At last, the second part was repeated while disabling the base augmentations mentioned in section 4.1 for every variation. This should show the effect of the base augmentations on our different networks. Both parts will test the performance on both the test set and the training set to provide precise insight into the training process.

Similarly to the previous experiment, lower learning rates are expected to perform worse due to the learning rate schedule. However, it is of interest if and how much better performance can be achieved with a longer training time. Moreover, the networks trained on the representative subset can be predicted to produce worse results than the ones utilizing the entire dataset. This should be even more pronounced with the removal of the base augmentations. However, it will be of interest to compare the performance dip due to the representative subset to the experiment from section 4.3.1.

4.3.4 Data augmentations

The following experiment deals with data augmentations. Their purpose is to create more data out of existing images. Thus the central question was: Can the model performance be optimized with image augmentations, and which augmentations show the best results for our use case?

First, the goal was to research different image augmentation methods and study their effect on model performance. Looking at the dataset, one could notice that most images were taken in colder seasons and depict traffic situations where the weather is greyish, and the lighting conditions are quite similar. The goal was to simulate various weather conditions in different seasons. Reproducing different conditions with these tools could make our model more robust and perform better. Therefore augmentation methods were chosen that will vary the colours and lighting of the images. Table 4.6 shows the different variations that were created. Each row represents a separate model, and a cross in a column corresponds to an applied augmentation method. The focus lies on four image parameters: Color, Contrast, Hue and Saturation. If an augmentation method is added, Tensorflow will randomly vary the set parameters on copies of images from the dataset and add them as training data. Note that variations that combine augmentation methods were also created. Figure 4.2 shows examples from the PETS dataset with varied hue in figure 4.2b and varied contrast in figure

4.2c.

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation
1	x			
2		x		
3			x	
4				x
5	x		x	
6	x			x
7	x	x		
8		x		x
9			x	x
10		x	x	
11	x	x	x	
12	x		x	x
13		x	x	x
14	x	x		x

Table 4.6: Image augmentation methods variations

Figure 4.2: Image from PETS with applied example augmentations

Like before, variations had to be trained that all use the base configuration as a starting point. However, image augmentation methods were added according to table 4.6.

In the end, a slight increase in precision can be expected due to the increased number and diversification of data. However, it is hard to tell in advance which method or combination of methods will perform the best. To illustrate this, consider figure 4.2 again. Varying the contrast (figure 4.2c) gives a more realistic simulation of a different lighting scenario which could cause the model to perform better. On the other hand, varying the hue (figure 4.2b) changes the colours so drastically that it could make the model recognize the actual shapes of a pedestrian more. Similarly, it will be interesting to see if adding more augmentations results in higher precision values.

4.3.5 Image resolutions

Finally, the last experiment investigates the effect of different input image resolutions and their consequences on performance. The central question is: Which image resolution fulfils the target time of less than 100ms and a maximum mAP loss of 2%?

This investigation consisted of taking the base model and creating variations where all parameters stayed the same except for the input resolution. Table 4.7 shows the different resolutions that have been tested. All chosen resolutions feature the same aspect ratio as the base resolution, allowing a fairer comparison.

ID	Resolution [px ²]
1	280 × 210
2	320 × 240
3	480 × 360
4	640 × 480
5	768 × 576

Table 4.7: Resolution variations

Lowering a resolution usually means decreasing the precision but also the latency. Consequently, this can be expected from this experiment, and it will be of interest how much these models drop compared to using the full resolution. However, it will also be compelling to see if and how much the target device choice affects the amount of decrease the models experience.

Chapter 5

Results

Now that the experiments and the training/testing setup have been investigated, it is time to focus on their results and interpretations. There will be many measurements for specific experiments, so only the most important results will be presented in this section. The complete collection of all measurements can be found in appendix A.

5.1 Dataset and subset

Device and quantization	Training	Validation	Mean latency [ms]	mAP at 0.5 IoU
CPU32	PETS	PETS	29.85	0.602
	PETS	All	29.98	0.602
	All	PETS	29.9	0.849
	All	All	30.23	0.839
GPU16	PETS	PETS	21.58	0.603
	PETS	All	21.64	0.601
	All	PETS	21.64	0.849
	All	All	21.65	0.848
GPU32	PETS	PETS	35.46	0.602
	PETS	All	35.5	0.602
	All	PETS	35.49	0.849
	All	All	35.46	0.839
MYRIAD16	PETS	PETS	188.79	0.603
	PETS	All	188.89	0.602
	All	PETS	188.86	0.849
	All	All	188.78	0.839

Table 5.1: Dataset and subset results

Table 5.1 shows the obtained results for all devices and quantizations. The training and validation columns indicate whether the entire dataset or the PETS subset has been used. Figure 5.1 offers better visualization of the measurements by showing the mAP for all variations grouped by device and quantization. The colour of the bars indicates which training and validation variation has been used, and it is additionally denoted in the legend descriptions with the letters "T" and "V".

First, it becomes apparent that the best-performing variations are the ones where the entire dataset has been used for training. The networks trained on the entire dataset perform more than 20% better than the models that used the PETS

Figure 5.1: MAP to device and quantization bar graph

subset. One more thing to add is that the models that were trained on the entire dataset and that used the PETS as a validation set perform slightly better than the version that used the entire test set as validation. Furthermore, roughly the same trends for every device and quantization can be observed. This parameter choice does not seem to affect the inference's precision.

Figure 5.2: Mean latency to device and quantization bar graph for models utilizing the entire dataset

Figure 5.2 shows the mean latency for every device and quantization of the models utilizing the entire dataset as a training and validation set. Additionally, a red line has been added at the maximum acceptable value of 100ms. Since training and validation set variations should not affect the latency of the inference, it is sufficient to look at one network in this regard. First of all, it can be seen that the GPU16 models have the fastest inference time, which makes sense due to the applied quantization. Furthermore, the CPU32 models perform better than the GPU32 models by approximately 5ms, meaning it might be better to use the CPU for 32-bit models. Finally, the MYRIAD16 models take the longest time with a mean latency of about 188ms, making them the only models that fall over 100ms.

In light of the observations, a few things become apparent. First, training on the entire dataset rather than the PETS subset is better. When trained on the entire training set, all three devices presented a performance increase of 20-25%.

This could be due to the diversification of the data, which probably helps the model become more general and thus perform better in different situations. It already makes sense if one considers the angles from where the pictures have been taken. To illustrate this, consider figure 5.3 which presents a the differences between subsets. For instance, the TUD-Stadtmitte sample picture from figure 5.3c and the PETS sample image from figure 5.3a present completely different viewpoints. Consequently, it would make sense that the detection is less precise when the model is presented with a new perspective. Additionally, the number of images could play a role since the PETS subset only features 1892 images compared to the total of 4532 images from the entire training set.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of viewpoints from subsets

Furthermore, the device and quantization do not seem to affect the precision of the models. However, it is a deciding factor for the inference time. For example, the GPU paired with a 16-bit quantized model performs the best with a mean latency of about 21ms even if the GPU32 and CPU32 models still quickly fulfil the latency constraint. This could be due to the optimized OpenVINO inference used on all devices.

All things considered, the ideal network from this experiment should be trained on the entire dataset, quantized to 16-bit and executed on the GPU. This would result in the highest precision while still having the fastest execution time.

5.2 Learning rate

Device and quantization	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
CPU32	0.144	0.839	0.832	0.753	0.620	0.420
GPU16	0	0.848	0.832	0.753	0.612	0.420
GPU32	0.144	0.839	0.832	0.753	0.620	0.420
MYRIAD16	0.024	0.839	0.832	0.746	0.613	0.414

Table 5.2: MAP values for various learning rates depending on the device and quantization

Table 5.2 shows the precision values for all learning rates, devices, and quantizations. Figure 5.4 shows these measurements depending on the learning rate on a logarithmic scale. Once again, the device and quantization do not gravely affect the model's precision. This behaviour will be expected for all remaining experiments. The only notable exception appears at the highest learning rate of 0.8, where the 32-bit models seem to perform better than the 16-bit models. Furthermore, for the agreed set of hyperparameters, the variations with the learning rates 0.08 and 0.008 perform the best at an accuracy comparable to the maximum of the first experiment. After that, the precision decreases gradually with every power of ten of the learning rate. The learning rate might be too low for the time the network has been trained. This might mean that if the number of steps is adapted according to the learning rate, the performance could get equal. However, the cosine learning rate schedule should not be forgotten. It gradually decreases the learning rate with the

number of steps. Nevertheless, this relation between the number of steps and the learning rate is the central theme of section 5.3 and will be investigated further. The worst performance is achieved by the network with the highest learning rate with an accuracy of 14-15% for the 32-bit models and approximately 0% for the 16-bit models. Training with such a high learning rate can cause the model to oscillate vastly over the optimum loss, which could have happened with this model. However, it seems like the higher quantization lessens this negative effect.

Figure 5.4: MAP to learning rate plot for all devices and quantizations

Given these points and the hyperparameters agreed upon for this experiment, the best network would be the one trained with a learning rate of 0.08, quantized to 16-bit and inferred on the GPU. This yields the highest accuracy with the lowest execution time.

5.3 Learning rate and number of steps

5.3.1 Entire dataset used for training

Learning Rate \ Number of steps	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.831	0.898	0.881	0.791	0.641	0.416
20000	0	0.879	0.892	0.835	0.715	0.515
50000	0	0.883	0.911	0.872	0.776	0.629
60000	0	0.899	0.916	0.878	0.786	0.650
90000	0	0.912	0.919	0.891	0.805	0.676
120000	0	0.912	0.919	0.895	0.815	0.691
130000	0	0.913	0.923	0.897	0.818	0.695
300000	0	0.917	0.921	0.901	0.836	0.713

Table 5.3: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the entire dataset

Tables 5.3 and 5.4 show a respective summary of the most important measurements. They highlight mAP values for every learning rate and certain step amounts for the inference with both the test and the training set. Additionally, figure 5.5 shows the mAP as a function of the number of training steps for the different learning rate variations again computed with both the test and training set. At first look, the models show roughly the same trends. The performance rises quickly but begins to converge after about 50 000 steps. Furthermore, the highest learning rate shows the worst

Number of steps \ Learning Rate	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.856	0.899	0.880	0.770	0.599	0.334
20000	0	0.919	0.904	0.827	0.688	0.464
50000	0	0.915	0.939	0.878	0.759	0.587
90000	0	0.945	0.949	0.900	0.795	0.640
120000	0	0.946	0.954	0.908	0.809	0.661
130000	0	0.950	0.954	0.910	0.810	0.667
300000	0	0.970	0.967	0.920	0.828	0.690

Table 5.4: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the entire dataset

Figure 5.5: Evolution of precision during training while using the entire dataset

performance. At first, the precision rises to an mAP of about 0.8 but plunges very quickly to a negligibly small value. After this, the models with learning rates of 0.00008 and 0.000008 follow. This behaviour stems from the cosine decaying learning rate schedule. Figure 5.6 shows how a learning rate of 0.0008 is scaled with this schedule. The learning rate starts from the warmup value to the actual learning rate and gradually decreases. This explains why the lower learning rates perform the way they do. They get stuck in a local minimum, and after the learning rate decreases, the step size becomes too small to get out of this local minimum in the time the network was trained. The schedule also explains the characteristics of the highest learning rate. The process starts at the warmup value, which is still a stable value for the network. After gradually increasing, values are reached, which can cause the network weights to go out of bounds. Consequently, the model will not yield very good detections. This raises the question of why Tensorflow built this schedule inside their model. The reason is that one can use high learning rates and profit from their ability to make our model learn faster while still being more robust to missing the actual minimum of the loss function because of a big step size that inherently comes from a high learning rate. Additionally, the top three learning rates reach a comparable performance and have values spread over a range of 10^3 values. This means it is also quite easy to find an acceptable value provided the training time is set adequately. However, as seen with the 0.8 learning rate, this does not simply work with any value.

When comparing the performance difference when evaluating the test or training dataset, the training set yields slightly higher accuracies ranging from 1-6 % after the entire training process. In the beginning, the performance is very similar, but the test set variations growth slows down in comparison to the training set variations. Consider, for instance, the 0.08 learning rate models: From step 120 000 to step 300 000, a performance increase of about 0.5% for the test set and 3% for the training set can be observed. This generally comes from the fact that the model has already seen the training

Figure 5.6: Cosine decay learning rate schedule with a learning rate of 0.0008

data. Consequently, it performs better on it than on the data it does not know yet. However, this difference varies from model to model. If this difference is slight, it could mean the model is overfitting after a particular duration, and the effect gets more pronounced with additional training time.

Thinking back to the previous experiment from section 5.2, one can compare the previously obtained mAP values with the ones at 60000 steps from table 5.3. The mAP differs from 4% to 14% depending on which learning rate. This is probably due to the model conversion to the IR format. The model optimizer changes the model structure to fit its IR format. As seen in section 2.3.2, there is variance in how accurately a network is converted, and this could result in a precision drop-off. This means it would be better to take a model directly provided by OpenVINO and try to avoid the conversion. However, this would not have been possible in this use case since a dedicated training with a custom dataset, and Tensorflow was necessary.

5.3.2 Reduced dataset used for training

Number of steps \ Learning Rate	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
10000	0.685	0.888	0.872	0.784	0.651	0.414
50000	0.748	0.891	0.895	0.874	0.778	0.632
100000	0.807	0.895	0.887	0.880	0.806	0.681
160000	0.871	0.901	0.879	0.885	0.823	0.702
200000	0.807	0.899	0.873	0.891	0.829	0.710
250000	0.854	0.888	0.875	0.893	0.831	0.714
300000	0.884	0.885	0.873	0.893	0.832	0.715

Table 5.5: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the reduced dataset and base augmentations

Number of steps \ Learning Rate	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
10000	0.708	0.921	0.884	0.767	0.614	0.322
50000	0.741	0.925	0.952	0.891	0.767	0.600
100000	0.863	0.959	0.963	0.915	0.805	0.654
160000	0.923	0.965	0.965	0.928	0.828	0.682
200000	0.836	0.965	0.967	0.934	0.833	0.690
250000	0.946	0.970	0.967	0.937	0.836	0.694
300000	0.969	0.969	0.967	0.936	0.837	0.695

Table 5.6: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the reduced dataset and base augmentations

Just like in section 5.3.1, tables 5.5 and 5.6 show a respective summary of the most important measurements. Figure 5.7

Figure 5.7: Evolution of precision during training while using the reduced dataset and base augmentations

presents the mAP as a function of the number of training steps for models that utilized the reduced dataset and base augmentations during training. First of all, the precision values are very comparable to before. This is a fascinating result compared to the considerable drop-off of the first experiment. Even though the models have access to fewer images, the data's diversification enables much better precision values. Additionally, the pre-training from Tensorflow certainly helps achieve a substantial mAP even though it did not have access to many images. However, approximately the same trends seen in section 5.3.1 for the learning rate can be observed. The test and training set show a gap in precision hovering at around 1-9%. This varies depending on the number of steps and the learning rate. This divergence is more prevalent for higher learning rates than for lower ones. The higher learning rate models yield a precision difference of about 6-9% while the lower ones of just 1-3%. Furthermore, the gap seems to increase with more steps for the models with learning rates of 0.08 and 0.008. At the same time, models with higher learning rates oscillate more between certain values. This becomes even clearer when inspecting the model with the highest learning rate. In contrast to section 5.3.1, it now yields useful precision values, but they oscillate vastly with differences in precision of 6% from one checkpoint to the next. Despite everything, the highest recorded precision value is attained with a learning rate of 0.08 and 160 000 training steps and is about 2% lower than the best model in section 5.3.1.

Number of steps \ Learning rate	Learning rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
10000	0.299	0.879	0.873	0.789	0.655	0.518
30000	0.629	0.913	0.897	0.850	0.753	0.652
70000	0.806	0.894	0.900	0.878	0.794	0.756
130000	0.696	0.886	0.881	0.895	0.817	0.785
140000	0.518	0.792	0.882	0.889	0.821	0.789
200000	0.861	0.897	0.869	0.897	0.830	0.798
250000	0.886	0.889	0.867	0.896	0.834	0.799
300000	0.886	0.886	0.867	0.897	0.835	0.801

Table 5.7: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the reduced dataset and no base augmentations

Tables 5.7 and 5.8 shows the most important results for models that used the reduced dataset and did not use base augmentations during training. Like before, figure 5.8 shows the mAP as a function of the number of steps for all models. At first, roughly the same trends can be observed with base augmentations applied or in section 5.3.1. In this case, a gap between the precision of the test and training data persists and ranges from 1-9%. Furthermore, it grows in most cases with an increasing number of steps. Similarly, there seems to be an improvement for the lowest learning rate on both training and test set. Moreover, models with higher learning rates oscillate even more than before. For

Number of steps \ Learning Rate	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
10000	0.243	0.904	0.889	0.774	0.606	0.497
30000	0.619	0.944	0.934	0.861	0.733	0.636
70000	0.784	0.944	0.956	0.903	0.785	0.757
130000	0.708	0.937	0.962	0.927	0.816	0.806
140000	0.495	0.852	0.964	0.925	0.819	0.809
200000	0.914	0.967	0.966	0.935	0.830	0.825
250000	0.951	0.973	0.966	0.936	0.836	0.829
300000	0.969	0.969	0.966	0.937	0.836	0.829

Table 5.8: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the reduced dataset and no base augmentations

instance, the model with a learning rate of 0.8 experiences a drop of almost 10% from steps 130000 and 140000. In total, the highest precision is attained for a learning rate of 0.08 and 30 000 steps and is about 1% worse than the models in section 5.3.1 that had access to the complete training set. However, it is significant to note that this precision value is higher than the best value with base augmentations.

Figure 5.8: Evolution of precision during training while using the reduced dataset and no base augmentations

All things considered, a few things become apparent. First, the precision is slightly higher when evaluating the training set compared to the test set. This is generally expected, as seen in section 5.3.1. However, the increase of the gap between the precisions and that the highest precision was reached at 160 000 steps for the models with base augmentations and 30 000 steps without base augmentations might indicate that the model is overfitting. Furthermore, a model without base augmentation attained the highest precision in this part of the experiment. Additionally, there was an improvement for the models with the lowest learning rates without base augmentations. This might be due to the nature of these augmentation methods, which revolve around positioning. These augmentations could boost performance but also hurt it because the models will yield less precise test data results that do not reflect situations where positional augmentations are beneficial. Therefore the models produce a lower precision value. However, data augmentations and their effects during training will be investigated in more detail in section 5.4. Moreover, the models with higher learning rates oscillate more than in section 5.3.1. This could stem from the fact that the models have access to less training data and thus become more unstable for higher learning rates. This idea could be reinforced by the fact that the oscillations become more pronounced when we remove the base augmentations because Tensorflow would then loop through the dataset over and over again instead of augmenting images and using those for the remaining training steps. That being said, an essential observation from this experiment comes from the fact that the size of the training set does not determine

how much time the training will take. The parameter determining the training time is the number of training steps set in the config file. As seen in section 5.3.1, if the dataset is too small for the number of steps and batch size, Tensorflow will automatically augment the dataset or loop through it until it has reached its set number of steps. This means using all the training data at one's disposal is most beneficial because it takes the same amount of time, obtains higher accuracies, and the models become more robust to oscillations. Nevertheless, 20% of the data resulted in a realistic picture of the general trends of the problem and comparable accuracies. However, the smaller dataset needs to represent the total dataset fairly, meaning that subset ratios need to be respected. This can be a vital insight considering the typical case where one has a custom unlabeled dataset. Annotating images is a long and tedious task, and this could mean that one could start by annotating a part of the dataset and performing experiments. These will give a realistic insight into the problem while the remaining data is being annotated.

Considering our given hyperparameters and measurements for this section, the ideal network would be a model trained with a learning rate of 0.008 and 130000 steps trained on the entire dataset. Moreover, it should be quantized to 16-bit and run on the GPU for a considerable latency speedup. Our research question, however, requires an answer in epochs. An epoch consists of one complete cycle through the training data. Consequently, the number of steps contained in one epoch can be calculated with:

$$n_{epoch} = \frac{m_{train}}{b_{size}} = \frac{4532}{32} = 141,625 \text{ steps} \quad (5.1)$$

where m_{train} is the number of training images and b_{size} is the batch size. In theory, the number of epochs for the top performing network can be calculated:

$$n = \frac{n_{steps}}{n_{epoch}} = \frac{130000}{141,625} \approx 918 \text{ epochs} \quad (5.2)$$

However, the base applied base augmentations need to be considered. To prevent overfitting, the object detection API automatically augments the dataset and feeds this new data into the network. As seen before, the entire dataset is passed 918 times. If we assume that the original dataset is passed once, the model will process:

$$n_{augmented} = 4532 \times 917 = 4155844 \text{ images} \quad (5.3)$$

where $n_{augmented}$ is the number of augmented images, which would be equally split over the two base augmentation methods. Nevertheless, the base augmentations did not seem ideal for the presented use case, so the next section will investigate different augmentation methods that might be better suited.

5.4 Data augmentations

Since the precision does not differ considerably between the different devices, table 5.9 shows the mAP values for GPU16 models. The "ID" column is a reference for figure 5.9, which presents these values in a bar plot. It should also be noted that a red line indicates the previous best comparable result of section 5.1. First of all, not all augmentations guarantee an improvement. For instance, the model trained with just a saturation augmentation performed about 1.5% worse than

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation	mAP at 0.5 IoU
1	x				0.849
2		x			0.850
3			x		0.845
4				x	0.837
5	x		x		0.860
6	x			x	0.859
7	x	x			0.858
8		x		x	0.847
9			x	x	0.842
10		x	x		0.850
11	x	x	x		0.857
12	x		x	x	0.858
13		x	x	x	0.849
14	x	x		x	0.850

Table 5.9: MAP for different image augmentation methods variations for GPU16 models

the base model. Furthermore, the single augmentations generally perform worse than the models utilizing combinations, with the best-performing variant being the one where Color and Hue augmentations are applied simultaneously. However, adding more augmentations does not necessarily increase performance. For instance, the model utilizing a single Saturation augmentation performs 1-2% worse than our base model from section 5.1. This also shows itself when one compares the model with id 5 and id 12. The second one only differs from the first by adding a Saturation augmentation to the mix, but the performance is slightly worse even with more differentiated augmentations. This observation can be extended to models with 1 or 2 augmentations. For instance, the model where Hue and Saturation were applied performed worse than the model with just a single Contrast augmentation. At last, all best-performing variants feature a Color augmentation which could arguably make it the most important one. Nevertheless, an interesting observation is that from the single augmentations, it is not the one with the best performance, but Contrast is.

Figure 5.9: MAP to applied augmentations bar graph for GPU16 models

Overall, the best-performing augmentation combination across all platforms affects Color and Hue. Comparing it with

the top performing network from section 5.1 featuring comparable parameters, there is an increase of about 1% in precision. This variant also outperformed models that combined these two augmentations with a third one. One could now say that Color and Hue are the best augmentations for this use case, and this might be right, but there is one more thing to consider. The idea behind this experiment was to simulate different lighting conditions that, for instance, can be due to the time of the day or seasons. Color and Hue augmentations perform the best on this dataset, and to be more specific on this test set. Our test set images are still taken from the same source datasets as the training set images. To achieve an accurate comparison, images from comparable traffic situations with different lighting would be needed, and the models should be tested with those. This would give a more realistic insight into how accurately these different conditions can be simulated with image augmentation methods. Additionally, combinations with three augmentation methods could perform better in this case. That said, image augmentation methods are still efficient since they boost the performance by about 1 % with no additional inference cost. Another aspect that needs to be considered is using a framework like Tensorflow’s Object Detection API. The additional development cost of utilizing these methods is minimal as a lot of the work is already done with the help of config files and pre-written training scripts that automatically augment images and add them as training data.

With all that in mind, one can say that the ideal network should utilize Color and Hue augmentations instead or alongside the base augmentations.

5.5 Resolutions

Device and quantization	Resolution [px ²]	Mean Latency [ms]	mAP at 0.5 IoU
CPU32	280 × 210	4.16	0.687
	320 × 240	5.03	0.741
	480 × 360	10.98	0.830
	640 × 480	20.39	0.854
	768 × 576	30.23	0.839
GPU16	280 × 210	7.59	0.687
	320 × 240	7.8	0.741
	480 × 360	11.28	0.829
	640 × 480	16.41	0.854
	768 × 576	21.65	0.848
GPU32	280 × 210	9	0.687
	320 × 240	9.8	0.741
	480 × 360	16.2	0.830
	640 × 480	26.08	0.854
	768 × 576	35.46	0.839
MYRIAD16	280 × 210	31.66	0.688
	320 × 240	37.46	0.741
	480 × 360	76.99	0.829
	640 × 480	130.84	0.853
	768 × 576	188.78	0.839

Table 5.10: Results for different image resolutions, devices and quantizations

Table 5.10 shows the results for different image resolutions and devices. Figure 5.10 presents these measurements in mAP to latency plots for each device. First, the different model variations now present a dissimilarity in inference time. The smaller the resolution is set, the lower the latency will be. At the same time, the difference in execution time decreases the lower the resolution is set. Furthermore, the CPU handles smaller resolutions better than the other devices. Every model with a resolution of 480 × 360px and lower is better suited for the CPU. The precision is the same while having

a reduced execution time. For example, it attained the lowest latency with 4.16ms for a resolution of 280×210 px. However, since the resolution also affects the precision of the model, the resulting precision reaches an unacceptable value of 68%. The GPU16 models at 640×480 px and 768×576 px offer a fast execution time at about 20ms with a still acceptable precision of about 84 – 85% with the former being the best performing variation. When looking at the GPU32 models, one can notice similar precision values but a difference in execution time that inherently comes from the quantization. However, this speed difference decreases with lower resolutions, so distinguishing between the 32 and 16-bit models becomes less significant. Finally, the MYRIAD16 models perform the worst of all. As seen in section 5.1, the precision values stay the same, but the inference time is much longer than on the other devices. However, the models with a resolution of 480×360 px or lower are now in an acceptable latency range. Nevertheless, a precision drop-off can be noted that only stays in an acceptable range of about 2% for the 480×360 px model.

Figure 5.10: MAP to latency plot for different resolutions and devices

All in all, the input resolution is one of the only investigated parameters that influence latency. This is due to the decreased dimension of the image, which reduces the computational complexity of the inference. The other parameters affecting the latency are the quantization and the device choice. As seen in section 5.1, the GPU alongside a 16-bit quantized model is usually the best choice except when using 32-bit models, which perform better on the CPU. Additionally, this experiment has shown that the CPU outperforms the GPU with smaller resolutions than 640×480 px. Notably, the 16-bit quantized models showed slower inference times than the CPU32 models.

Given these points, the resolutions fulfilling the constraints on latency and precision are:

- 768×576 px for CPU and GPU
- 640×480 px for CPU and GPU
- 480×360 px for CPU, GPU and Myriad

However, the best network has an input resolution of 640×480 px. This probably originates from the fact that this the original size of the TUD-Stadtmitte pictures. Furthermore, the network should be quantized to 16bit and run on the GPU. Therefore, it has the highest accuracy while effortlessly passing the latency constraint.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

It is now time to recapitulate all observations. This will be done by describing the entire workflow from training to inference to obtain the best-performing model for this specific use case.

First, it is advantageous to train the network on the entire dataset. Not only does the model have access to more images, but the subsets also present different viewpoints of a pedestrian crossing. This could make the network more robust to different angles from which a camera can be placed. In this case, an increase of 20-25% was recorded when using the entire dataset compared to the PETS subset. Furthermore, there is no time gain when using fewer images. With Tensorflow's Object Detection API, the decisive factor determining the duration of the training process is the number of training steps and not the number of images passed into the network for training. However, one can gain already notable insights into the trends with fewer images. A representative dataset that respects the subset divisions and features 20% of the data resulted in comparable accuracies. This can be a time-saving factor for the case when a custom dataset is not already fully annotated. Additionally, 20% of diversified data from the total dataset performed considerably better than just using one subset. This shows that for this use case, the data's diversification seems more important than having access to more images showing the same traffic situations.

This leads to the topic of image augmentations. Suppose there are not enough images for the chosen batch size and the number of training steps. In that case, Tensorflow's Object Detection API automatically augments the dataset with specified augmentation methods or loops the dataset if no augmentations are applied until we reach the desired training steps. Therefore, it is advantageous to choose some augmentation, so the dataset will not be looped repeatedly and cause a more unstable training process or increase the chance of overfitting. Additionally, image augmentations offer a potential performance increase that is very easy to set up with frameworks like Tensorflow and presents no additional inference cost. However, some augmentations are better suited than others, and for instance, Tensorflow's base augmentations, which apply positional transformations, did not seem to be ideal candidates for the problem. For this use case, the effect of augmentations which affect the image's colouration in different ways has been investigated. The number of augmentations and the nature of these methods have been varied. In conclusion, the best performing combination was the one with augmentations affecting Color and Hue simultaneously, which increased the precision to about 1%.

Let us now focus on the ideal number of training steps and the associated learning rate for this use case. First, the model's base setup inhibits a cosine decay learning rate schedule. This allows for higher learning rate values while

maintaining a stable training process where one will not miss the optimum because of the large step size. Consequently, a more considerable learning rate should be chosen from the start since a value that is too small can cause the model to get stuck in a local minimum if the step size is too small. Overall, the best performing combination of a learning rate of 0.008 and 130000 steps resulted in a precision of 92.3% with Tensorflow's Inference.

Finally, the last parameter set up during training is the input resolution of the images. In contrast to the other parameters seen until now, this affects the precision and inference time. After the experiments, the ideal resolution is 640×480 px. This resolution yields the highest precision while offering a slight inference time boost compared to the highest resolution of 768×576 px. Resolutions even lower than 640×480 px offer a further decrease in inference time. However, a maximum of 2% precision drop off from 85% from the first experiment was tolerated. This theoretically includes the 480×360 px resolutions. Nevertheless, since the latency target is easily attained for the GPU and CPU, the increased precision of the 640×480 px models seems to be more advantageous.

Let us move on to the conversion, the model's inference, and the target device choice. First of all, it seems like the conversion is hurting the precision of the models. This could be due to the nature of the conversion. As seen in section 2.3.2, the conversion quality differs from model to model and framework to framework. If one wants to use OpenVINO's inference engine, it might be better to take a model from the OpenVINO Model Zoo if no custom training is required. However, the Tensorflow 2 support was new at the time of the thesis and could change over time resulting in a more precise conversion. Nevertheless, Open VINO's optimized Inference Engine for Intel Hardware facilitates the fulfilment of the latency constraint. The CPU and GPU are a fair bit below the 100ms limit for all experiments. For a resolution of 768×576 px, the CPU shows execution times of about 30ms, while the GPU offers execution times of 35ms for 32-Bit models and 21ms for 16-Bit models. Consequently, 32bit models are better suited to run on a CPU. Moving on to the NCS2, it mostly hovered around 175ms, which is far too slow. The only exception was the just before mentioned case where the input resolution was decreased. A resolution of 480×360 px or less will fulfil the constraint in latency. Nevertheless, this speedup in inference time comes with a notable price of precision that accentuates the more the resolution is scaled down. Additionally, the higher resolutions run faster on GPU and CPU making the drop in accuracy unnecessary if one has access to these devices. One more thing to add is that the CPU seems to outperform even the GPU 16-bit models when a smaller resolution is chosen than 480×360 px. However, this also results in an unacceptable accuracy drop-off. Overall, the GPU seems to be the best choice because it can run 16- and 32-bit models while maintaining the same precision and being the fastest device when running 16-bit models with all agreed parameters.

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Appendix A

Result tables

A.1 Dataset and subset

Device and quantization	Training	Validation	Mean latency [ms]	mAP at 0.5 IoU
CPU32	PETS	PETS	29.85	0.602
	PETS	All	29.98	0.602
	All	PETS	29.9	0.849
	All	All	30.23	0.839
GPU16	PETS	PETS	21.58	0.603
	PETS	All	21.64	0.601
	All	PETS	21.64	0.849
	All	All	21.65	0.848
GPU32	PETS	PETS	35.46	0.602
	PETS	All	35.5	0.602
	All	PETS	35.49	0.849
	All	All	35.46	0.839
MYRIAD16	PETS	PETS	188.79	0.603
	PETS	All	188.89	0.602
	All	PETS	188.86	0.849
	All	All	188.78	0.839

Table A.1: Dataset and subset results

A.2 Learning rate

Device and quantization	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
CPU32	0.144	0.839	0.832	0.753	0.620	0.420
GPU16	0	0.848	0.832	0.753	0.612	0.420
GPU32	0.144	0.839	0.832	0.753	0.620	0.420
MYRIAD16	0.024	0.839	0.832	0.746	0.613	0.414

Table A.2: MAP values for various learning rates depending on the device and quantization

A.3 Learning rate and number of steps

A.3.1 Entire dataset used for training

Learning Rate \ Number of steps	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.831	0.898	0.881	0.791	0.641	0.416
20000	0	0.879	0.892	0.835	0.715	0.515
30000	0	0.899	0.899	0.855	0.747	0.563
40000	0	0.892	0.912	0.871	0.762	0.599
50000	0	0.882	0.911	0.872	0.776	0.629
60000	0	0.899	0.916	0.878	0.786	0.650
70000	0	0.904	0.916	0.881	0.792	0.663
80000	0	0.907	0.918	0.887	0.799	0.671
90000	0	0.912	0.919	0.891	0.805	0.676
100000	0	0.915	0.921	0.892	0.809	0.683
110000	0	0.905	0.921	0.894	0.813	0.691
120000	0	0.912	0.919	0.895	0.815	0.691
130000	0	0.913	0.923	0.897	0.818	0.695
140000	0	0.916	0.921	0.896	0.820	0.699
150000	0	0.909	0.914	0.898	0.825	0.702
160000	0	0.916	0.916	0.896	0.827	0.707
170000	0	0.916	0.921	0.902	0.827	0.706
180000	0	0.921	0.920	0.902	0.829	0.709
190000	0	0.916	0.923	0.899	0.830	0.712
200000	0	0.916	0.918	0.902	0.832	0.712
210000	0	0.925	0.921	0.901	0.833	0.712
220000	0	0.920	0.920	0.901	0.834	0.714
230000	0	0.922	0.920	0.902	0.836	0.713
240000	0	0.916	0.923	0.901	0.834	0.718
250000	0	0.913	0.922	0.901	0.835	0.715
260000	0	0.919	0.922	0.901	0.835	0.715
270000	0	0.912	0.923	0.902	0.836	0.712
280000	0	0.918	0.926	0.902	0.835	0.714
290000	0	0.918	0.922	0.901	0.836	0.716
300000	0	0.917	0.921	0.902	0.836	0.713

Table A.3: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the entire dataset

Learning Rate \ Number of steps	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.856	0.899	0.880	0.770	0.600	0.334
20000	0	0.919	0.904	0.827	0.688	0.464
30000	0	0.924	0.926	0.852	0.727	0.531
40000	0	0.924	0.936	0.871	0.745	0.564
50000	0	0.915	0.939	0.878	0.759	0.587
60000	0	0.935	0.943	0.884	0.771	0.609
70000	0	0.937	0.944	0.889	0.780	0.623
80000	0	0.931	0.949	0.897	0.788	0.632
90000	0	0.945	0.949	0.900	0.795	0.641
100000	0	0.947	0.951	0.903	0.800	0.649
110000	0	0.936	0.950	0.906	0.804	0.659
120000	0	0.946	0.954	0.908	0.809	0.661
130000	0	0.950	0.954	0.910	0.810	0.667
140000	0	0.944	0.952	0.913	0.814	0.672
150000	0	0.950	0.955	0.913	0.817	0.674
160000	0	0.950	0.955	0.915	0.819	0.681
170000	0	0.954	0.958	0.917	0.821	0.681
180000	0	0.957	0.960	0.918	0.823	0.684
190000	0	0.959	0.957	0.919	0.824	0.687
200000	0	0.959	0.956	0.920	0.824	0.687
210000	0	0.963	0.961	0.921	0.826	0.689
220000	0	0.961	0.961	0.920	0.826	0.690
230000	0	0.965	0.960	0.920	0.828	0.690
240000	0	0.963	0.962	0.921	0.828	0.694
250000	0	0.968	0.963	0.920	0.828	0.692
260000	0	0.968	0.960	0.921	0.828	0.692
270000	0	0.969	0.960	0.921	0.829	0.690
280000	0	0.970	0.962	0.921	0.827	0.692
290000	0	0.970	0.963	0.921	0.829	0.693
300000	0	0.970	0.963	0.920	0.828	0.691

Table A.4: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the entire dataset

A.3.2 Reduced dataset used for training

Number of steps	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.685	0.888	0.872	0.784	0.651	0.414
20000	0.783	0.897	0.885	0.831	0.720	0.533
30000	0.793	0.862	0.893	0.849	0.749	0.579
40000	0.563	0.884	0.896	0.863	0.766	0.608
50000	0.748	0.891	0.895	0.874	0.778	0.632
60000	0.794	0.891	0.894	0.875	0.785	0.648
70000	0.854	0.892	0.896	0.876	0.793	0.661
80000	0.850	0.839	0.893	0.868	0.798	0.672
90000	0.813	0.891	0.885	0.877	0.801	0.672
100000	0.808	0.895	0.887	0.880	0.806	0.681
110000	0.844	0.892	0.884	0.885	0.809	0.687
120000	0.799	0.873	0.886	0.885	0.811	0.693
130000	0.827	0.883	0.885	0.889	0.815	0.696
140000	0.835	0.892	0.885	0.885	0.817	0.698
150000	0.829	0.898	0.877	0.886	0.820	0.702
160000	0.871	0.901	0.879	0.885	0.823	0.702
170000	0.874	0.895	0.877	0.890	0.826	0.708
180000	0.816	0.889	0.882	0.891	0.825	0.707
190000	0.826	0.882	0.881	0.889	0.829	0.709
200000	0.807	0.899	0.873	0.891	0.829	0.710
210000	0.875	0.898	0.879	0.892	0.830	0.713
220000	0.851	0.877	0.875	0.892	0.831	0.715
230000	0.825	0.894	0.873	0.892	0.831	0.713
240000	0.886	0.880	0.872	0.891	0.832	0.715
250000	0.854	0.888	0.875	0.893	0.831	0.714
260000	0.888	0.890	0.875	0.892	0.832	0.714
270000	0.885	0.884	0.874	0.892	0.832	0.714
280000	0.881	0.889	0.873	0.892	0.832	0.715
290000	0.880	0.884	0.874	0.892	0.831	0.715
300000	0.884	0.885	0.873	0.893	0.832	0.715

Table A.5: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the reduced dataset and base augmentations

Number of steps	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.708	0.921	0.884	0.767	0.614	0.322
20000	0.820	0.919	0.924	0.831	0.698	0.484
30000	0.843	0.921	0.935	0.857	0.735	0.547
40000	0.632	0.943	0.948	0.880	0.754	0.576
50000	0.741	0.925	0.952	0.891	0.767	0.600
60000	0.842	0.951	0.958	0.896	0.776	0.617
70000	0.887	0.948	0.955	0.904	0.785	0.631
80000	0.878	0.915	0.959	0.902	0.792	0.640
90000	0.877	0.953	0.963	0.912	0.799	0.647
100000	0.863	0.959	0.963	0.915	0.805	0.654
110000	0.878	0.948	0.962	0.922	0.810	0.662
120000	0.873	0.948	0.963	0.923	0.813	0.669
130000	0.882	0.943	0.960	0.925	0.820	0.672
140000	0.890	0.958	0.964	0.927	0.822	0.675
150000	0.887	0.965	0.965	0.929	0.826	0.680
160000	0.923	0.965	0.965	0.928	0.828	0.682
170000	0.920	0.969	0.964	0.932	0.831	0.686
180000	0.864	0.970	0.966	0.933	0.830	0.685
190000	0.868	0.963	0.967	0.934	0.833	0.689
200000	0.836	0.965	0.967	0.934	0.833	0.690
210000	0.936	0.969	0.967	0.935	0.835	0.693
220000	0.919	0.968	0.967	0.935	0.836	0.694
230000	0.906	0.973	0.966	0.936	0.836	0.693
240000	0.953	0.972	0.967	0.936	0.837	0.695
250000	0.946	0.971	0.967	0.937	0.836	0.694
260000	0.963	0.970	0.966	0.936	0.837	0.695
270000	0.969	0.969	0.967	0.937	0.836	0.695
280000	0.970	0.969	0.967	0.937	0.836	0.695
290000	0.969	0.969	0.967	0.936	0.836	0.695
300000	0.970	0.969	0.967	0.936	0.837	0.695

Table A.6: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the reduced dataset and base augmentations

Number of steps \ Learning rate	Learning rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.299	0.879	0.873	0.789	0.655	0.518
20000	0.147	0.823	0.902	0.830	0.718	0.604
30000	0.629	0.912	0.897	0.850	0.753	0.652
40000	0.803	0.889	0.905	0.865	0.769	0.697
50000	0.686	0.884	0.899	0.870	0.784	0.724
60000	0.725	0.872	0.883	0.875	0.791	0.742
70000	0.806	0.894	0.900	0.878	0.794	0.756
80000	0.600	0.889	0.898	0.881	0.799	0.763
90000	0.775	0.901	0.897	0.880	0.805	0.770
100000	0.786	0.891	0.895	0.884	0.808	0.774
110000	0.804	0.899	0.888	0.886	0.813	0.777
120000	0.767	0.870	0.884	0.890	0.815	0.782
130000	0.696	0.886	0.881	0.895	0.817	0.785
140000	0.518	0.792	0.882	0.887	0.821	0.789
150000	0.821	0.897	0.880	0.893	0.821	0.790
160000	0.872	0.906	0.883	0.894	0.825	0.792
170000	0.730	0.905	0.884	0.895	0.826	0.796
180000	0.740	0.890	0.871	0.895	0.829	0.798
190000	0.860	0.895	0.886	0.895	0.830	0.797
200000	0.861	0.897	0.869	0.897	0.830	0.798
210000	0.862	0.888	0.870	0.895	0.831	0.800
220000	0.881	0.899	0.872	0.896	0.831	0.798
230000	0.865	0.891	0.872	0.896	0.832	0.802
240000	0.899	0.887	0.875	0.896	0.832	0.801
250000	0.886	0.889	0.867	0.896	0.834	0.799
260000	0.853	0.886	0.868	0.897	0.834	0.801
270000	0.892	0.892	0.868	0.897	0.834	0.801
280000	0.891	0.887	0.868	0.897	0.835	0.802
290000	0.885	0.886	0.867	0.896	0.835	0.801
300000	0.886	0.886	0.867	0.897	0.835	0.801

Table A.7: MAP values for inference with test data for models trained with the reduced dataset and no base augmentations

Number of steps \ Learning Rate	Learning Rate					
	0.8	0.08	0.008	0.0008	0.00008	0.000008
0	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356	0.356
10000	0.243	0.904	0.889	0.774	0.606	0.497
20000	0.095	0.832	0.930	0.833	0.699	0.588
30000	0.619	0.944	0.934	0.861	0.733	0.636
40000	0.842	0.938	0.949	0.877	0.751	0.685
50000	0.760	0.950	0.950	0.888	0.765	0.721
60000	0.733	0.935	0.952	0.897	0.778	0.742
70000	0.784	0.944	0.956	0.903	0.785	0.757
80000	0.565	0.954	0.963	0.908	0.793	0.769
90000	0.755	0.953	0.962	0.913	0.799	0.778
100000	0.833	0.950	0.963	0.917	0.804	0.786
110000	0.844	0.963	0.957	0.921	0.810	0.793
120000	0.792	0.946	0.963	0.925	0.812	0.800
130000	0.708	0.937	0.962	0.927	0.816	0.806
140000	0.495	0.852	0.964	0.925	0.819	0.809
150000	0.884	0.957	0.963	0.929	0.820	0.813
160000	0.900	0.962	0.964	0.929	0.827	0.816
170000	0.732	0.967	0.965	0.931	0.828	0.820
180000	0.774	0.966	0.961	0.932	0.830	0.822
190000	0.914	0.969	0.966	0.933	0.832	0.823
200000	0.914	0.967	0.966	0.935	0.831	0.825
210000	0.911	0.969	0.966	0.935	0.832	0.825
220000	0.931	0.969	0.968	0.935	0.833	0.826
230000	0.939	0.969	0.967	0.936	0.834	0.828
240000	0.949	0.969	0.966	0.935	0.834	0.829
250000	0.951	0.973	0.966	0.936	0.836	0.829
260000	0.933	0.969	0.967	0.936	0.835	0.830
270000	0.963	0.973	0.966	0.936	0.836	0.830
280000	0.965	0.971	0.966	0.937	0.837	0.830
290000	0.969	0.969	0.966	0.936	0.839	0.829
300000	0.970	0.969	0.966	0.937	0.836	0.829

Table A.8: MAP values for inference with training data for models trained with the reduced dataset and no base augmentations

A.4 Data augmentations

A.4.1 CPU

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation	mAP at 0.5 IoU
1	x				0.849
2		x			0.850
3			x		0.845
4				x	0.837
5	x		x		0.860
6	x			x	0.859
7	x	x			0.858
8		x		x	0.847
9			x	x	0.842
10		x	x		0.850
11	x	x	x		0.857
12	x		x	x	0.859
13		x	x	x	0.849
14	x	x		x	0.850

Table A.9: MAP for different image augmentation methods variations for CPU32 models

A.4.2 GPU

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation	mAP at 0.5 IoU
1	x				0.849
2		x			0.850
3			x		0.845
4				x	0.837
5	x		x		0.860
6	x			x	0.859
7	x	x			0.858
8		x		x	0.847
9			x	x	0.842
10		x	x		0.850
11	x	x	x		0.857
12	x		x	x	0.858
13		x	x	x	0.849
14	x	x		x	0.850

Table A.10: MAP for different image augmentation methods variations for GPU16 models

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation	mAP at 0.5 IoU
1	x				0.849
2		x			0.850
3			x		0.845
4				x	0.837
5	x		x		0.860
6	x			x	0.859
7	x	x			0.858
8		x		x	0.847
9			x	x	0.842
10		x	x		0.850
11	x	x	x		0.857
12	x		x	x	0.859
13		x	x	x	0.849
14	x	x		x	0.850

Table A.11: MAP for different image augmentation methods variations for GPU32 models

A.4.3 Myriad VPU

Model ID	Color	Contrast	Hue	Saturation	mAP at 0.5 IoU
1	x				0.849
2		x			0.849
3			x		0.845
4				x	0.837
5	x		x		0.860
6	x			x	0.859
7	x	x			0.859
8		x		x	0.847
9			x	x	0.842
10		x	x		0.850
11	x	x	x		0.857
12	x		x	x	0.858
13		x	x	x	0.849
14	x	x		x	0.850

Table A.12: MAP for different image augmentation methods variations for MYRIAD16 models

A.5 Resolutions

Device and quantization	Resolution [px ²]	Mean Latency [ms]	mAP at 0.5 IoU
CPU32	280×210	4.16	0.687
	320×240	5.03	0.741
	480×360	10.98	0.830
	640×480	20.39	0.854
	768×576	30.23	0.839
GPU16	280 × 210	7.59	0.687
	320 × 240	7.8	0.741
	480 × 360	11.28	0.829
	640 × 480	16.41	0.854
	768 × 576	21.65	0.848
GPU32	280 × 210	9	0.687
	320 × 240	9.8	0.741
	480 × 360	16.2	0.830
	640 × 480	26.08	0.854
	768 × 576	35.46	0.839
MYRIAD16	280 × 210	31.66	0.688
	320 × 240	37.46	0.741
	480 × 360	76.99	0.829
	640 × 480	130.84	0.853
	768 × 576	188.78	0.839

Table A.13: Results for different image resolutions, devices and quantizations

Erklärung zur Verfassung der Arbeit

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass die vorliegende Arbeit gemäß dem Code of Conduct – Regeln zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis (in der aktuellen Fassung des jeweiligen Mitteilungsblattes der TU Wien), insbesondere ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel, angefertigt wurde. Die aus anderen Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Daten und Konzepte sind unter Angabe der Quelle gekennzeichnet. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im In- noch im Ausland in gleicher oder in ähnlicher Form in anderen Prüfungsverfahren vorgelegt.

Vienna, Austria December 2022

Julian Westra